

Superman 2025 Ian Gordon

[In June 2025 the *New York Times* asked me for an Op-Ed on why Superman is popular enough to warrant another film. Then yesterday they, and I quote, decided “to go in another direction.” Other direction = Junot Diaz. It was too late to place the piece elsewhere. So here it is.]

Superman’s continued popularity remains great enough that a new film version *Superman* (2025) opens today. It might seem a brave move to make an expensive film (estimates suggest costs as high as 400 million including marketing) despite the underwhelming critical response to the last two film iterations, *Superman Returns* (2007) and *Man of Steel* (2013). Part of the reason for taking the risk is that Superman is so popular, and so widely licensed, that ticket sales and profits from the movie are only a part of corporate owner Warner Bros.’s considerations in undertaking such a venture.

Banner for *Superman* (2025) on Doubletree Hotel, Brussels, June 2025.

Superman is ubiquitous in American culture. Thousands of products carry his licensed image for instance, the Yankee bobblehead for June this year featuring Aaron Judge opening his shirt revealing Superman’s logo. Superman also features in numerous

songs including those by Laurie Anderson and REM. He even crops up in Viet Thanh Nguyen's Pulitzer Prize winning novel *The Sympathizer*. These are just a few of the ways that Superman occupies an iconic space in American culture.

The reaction to trailers for *Superman (2025)* has the *Hollywood Reporter* suggesting the film might generate a billion dollars revenue. From what I have seen the film will compare favorably to the Christopher Reeve 1978 film, which represented a breakthrough in bringing Superman to the screen. That film lived up to the hype of believing a man could fly. More importantly, in the aftermath of the war in Vietnam, and of Watergate, it delivered a Superman who rejected the cynicism of the era.

How has a character dreamed up by two Cleveland kids, Jerry Siegel and Joe Shuster, and who first appeared in a 1938 comic book, maintained such a grip on the American imagination? Superman at his best represents the promise of American life, he fights for the American way, and although there are numerous limitations and nuances to what that means, being kind and committed to doing good are values essential to Superman and ones many Americans think capture the essence of the country.

In his first appearance Superman raced to save a wrongly convicted man from being executed. Although possessing the power to intervene directly at the prison Superman operated within the law convincing a state Governor to stay the execution. Over the years as Superman became more powerful, and appeared in more media, such as comic strips (1939), radio (1940), animated cartoons (1941), television (1952), and film (1978), he constrained his actions to aiding humans in need rather than engaging in a large-scale reshaping of the world.

During World War II Superman was enormously popular with the troops and the Army distributed an overseas service edition of the comic book. Because clearly a fictional superhero could not end the war Superman chose to let American soldiers fight and win the war displaying a faith in the power of democracy. It was during the war that Superman first started fighting for "the American way," which was added to the "truth and justice" section of the opening monologue of the Superman radio serial after the attack on Pearl Harbor. In her book on the American way Wendy Wall shows that use of the term in the 1930s cut across the political spectrum and that its meaning was so

unclear that *Harpers* ran a contest trying to clarify the matter. By WWII the American way was understood as a national consensus. Tension existed between consensus as a broad civility, with accompanying limits to debate and change, or consensus resting on equality as a structural underpinning and so requiring action to achieve that state. Such tensions were somewhat abated by the promise of postwar prosperity for all. The American way nonetheless remained a vague concept full of ambiguity and this was part of its appeal. The American way was also not a set of values but a process in which everyone theoretically had the same opportunities for success.

Superman's association with the American way carried over to the 1950s television series that opened with a similar opening monologue to the radio serial. While the announcer intoned Superman's "never ending battle for truth, justice, and the American way" star George Reeves segued from Clark Kent to Superman in front of a fluttering American flag. The television series rooted the American way as Superman's mission to such an extent that Christopher Reeve, the star of the 1978 film *Superman*, told an interviewer that Superman was a hero because he believed and fought for "truth, justice, and the American way." In the film Superman states this explicitly much to the disbelief of the cynical Lois Lane.

The American way and the consensus and civility of WWII were for Americans and not even all of them as Japanese Americans rounded up and put in concentration camps could attest. Flawed as it was the American way and the promise of prosperity was often aspirational for those previously excluded by race, class, or even nationality. By 1978 when Reeve proclaimed his support for the American way Superman had become such an international phenomenon that the movie took 55.3 percent (\$166 million) of its revenue from the international market and the American take was only 44.7 percent (\$134 million) of the total. In contrast, the original Star Wars movie of 1977 sold 60 percent of its tickets in the United States and only 40 percent in international markets. To equate international audiences' appetite for a Superman film with say an alignment with American interests would be too easy. But Superman fighting for the American way is an invitation for audiences to engage with their own understanding of what that might mean. The American way is a promise requiring realization through human agency. Superman's fight is not a defense of the status quo, but a struggle for the human values he holds dear: kindness and civility. The 2006 film

Superman Returns obliquely referenced the American way by making Superman's fight for "truth, justice, and all that stuff." In 2021 DC comics recast the phrase as "truth, justice, and a better tomorrow," which closely matched the WWII meaning of the American way. Both these efforts at rewording the phrase still retained its traces.

A constant in Superman over the years has been the conflict between his alien origin and his human rearing. Writers including Elliot S. Maggin, John Byrne, Alan Moore, Mark Waid, and Grant Morrison with artist Frank Quietly, have emphasized Superman's humanity with a set of values and sense of self shaped by his upbringing. Such stories lend themselves to interpretations of Superman as the ultimate assimilated immigrant with his humanity firmly grounded in his middle-American rearing. Publicity for *Superman (2025)* mentions that the film's director James Gunn has drawn inspiration from several of these writers' Superman stories. And Gunn's Superman fights for "truth, justice, and the human way." If this seems progressive, or for conservatives retrograde, then it is best to remember America's long history of denying the humanity of different races and its opponents. Superman still carries the tension of the American way between a consensus civility and a struggle for equality. I expect that *Superman (2025)* will succeed at the box office and beyond because it will deliver a Superman whose human way is recognizably American for the domestic market and just enough distanced from less attractive aspect of the country to appeal to international audiences. The promise might be deferred but the values worth fighting for remain.